

HR Practices in Support of Green Initiatives

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Abstract

The corporate world is evolving from an environmental standpoint to a financial one. Every organization wants to support environmental sustainability in order to better meet their needs in the future. Combining environmental management with human resource management is known as "Green HRM." It is made up of two components: preservation of intellectual capital and environmental friendliness. The phrase "green human resource" describes HR initiatives that support sustainable and environmentally friendly resource use.

Keywords: environmentally friendly, sustainable, eco-friendly human resource management

Introduction

Organizations are increasingly pursuing green HRM in order to ensure the long-term sustainability of natural resources. Green HR practices include things like online interviews, teleconferences, carpooling, electronic forms, virtual interviews, and more. Before making a business decision, an organization must assume responsibility for social and environmental challenges. The majority of the organization implemented the "3 R" (Reduce, Reuse, and Recycling) approach to lower operating costs and promote environmental sustainability. The organization should switch to green HR practices now to ensure sustainable use of natural resources for a longer lifespan and to benefit society.

For the smooth operation of the business and protection of the environment, public Indian companies such as Bharat Heavy Electrical Ltd., Bharat Dynamics Ltd., National Minerals Development Corporation, Hindustan Aeronautics Ltd., and Neyveli Lignite Corporation Ltd. are

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implementing green HR practices for their employees. Integrating environmental sustainability into human resource management is crucial for organizations. The significance of green human resource management.

Using green HR techniques in human resource management is crucial for organizations. The primary goals of implementing green HRM are to save operating costs, attract and retain talented employees, obtain a competitive edge, fulfill corporate social responsibility, boost employee morale, and develop the company's brand, among other goals.

Green HRM combines natural resource management with human resource management to promote environmental sustainability and efficient use of natural resources. Integrating green HR practices into HR procedures aids in establishing an eco-advantage culture inside the organization, assessing environmental problems, and attempting to resolve them by integrating an environment management system into corporate strategy.

The study's objectives

- ✓ to examine green HR practices and policy. to comprehend the benefits and difficulties associated with implementing green HRM.
- ✓ Eco-Friendly Purchasing
- ✓ Green recruitment and the organization's green human resource selection procedure make up green procurement.

These days, a lot of businesses request employee information via emails and websites in order to fill positions. Green HR practices include telecommuting, online interviews, and virtual interviews for choosing applicants. It results in a decrease in travel time, energy consumption, expenses, and pollution of the environment. Fix the green criteria during the selection process in order to draw in qualified and skilled candidates who use the green criteria. Choosing the appropriate person for the task at the right moment is crucial for the organization.

Environmental Education and Training

Online training, teleconferencing, video calls, online case studies and course materials, web-based training modules, and interactive media are all considered forms of green training that contribute to improving employee productivity in green HR practices. Management development is a crucial component of green HR practices, and learning plans should incorporate seminars, workshops, and other programs to help staff members advance their understanding of environmental management. Employees are encouraged to work with great energy and enthusiasm in the organization through Green Compensation and Reward Compensation. Employers add two types of pay to their employee packages: monetary and non-monetary, based on the employee's achievement, contribution, and acquisition of green skills in HR practices.

The implementation of green HR techniques, such as online course materials, teleconferencing, video calls, and teletraining, can boost employee productivity. Incentivizing employees to contribute to the environment through rewards and recognition such as promotions, awards, public acclaim, and appreciation are other strategies.

Techniques for Green Performance Appraisals

Organizations use performance appraisal methods that include a scale for green HR practices, such as familiarizing employees with environmental issues, raising awareness of pollution control, reducing pollution, promoting sustainability in the environment, and involving and engaging environmental management as a key performance area for all employee levels to participate in the environment management system. The organization outlines the green targets, goals, and responsibilities of each employee. It also takes these into account when evaluating an employee's performance in order to ensure that the organization's green policies are implemented.

Green Business Partnership

An organization dedicated to green concerns pertaining to workers' health, safety, and working conditions as well as environmentally sustainable methods that boost employee motivation must run an environment awareness campaign. Green workplace policies include flexible work schedules, carpooling, free public transportation, telecommuting, encouraging employees to use eco-friendly products, discouraging the use of plastic and glass, and supporting their involvement in environmental initiatives as well as in green suggestion schemes and programs. Employee involvement in the green management system increases as a result.

Mechanism for Green Redressals

Employee behavior is hard to change for the purpose of implementing green HRM. Establishing a stringent policy for green HR practices within the organization is crucial. Enforcing corrective action against employees' environmentally unfriendly behavior and grievances related to environmental issues is necessary.

Advantages of using green human resource management

- ✓ It engages in environmental issues and gives people a sense of fulfillment in their work. Getting a competitive advantage is a must for any organization.
- ✓ The hiring of applicants with green talent results in lower expenses for organizing conferences, seminars, and awareness campaigns.
- ✓ Online training and teleconferences cut employee travel expenses and time, improve pollution control, and lower carbon emissions.
- ✓ It contributes to lower labor turnover and greater employee retention.

- ✓ It builds the organization's reputation and draws in skilled candidates.
- ✓ Enhancing relationships with all stakeholders and the public helps the organization preserve ecological equilibrium.
- ✓ It helps the business acquire a competitive edge in both the market and the industry.
- ✓ It contributes to lowering carbon emissions and global warming. Green HRM implementation challenges Recruiting candidates with green talent can be challenging for organizations.
- ✓ Bridging the human resource touch gap between the organization and conducting all events virtually presents challenges.
- ✓ When workers are compelled to support environmental sustainability, it makes those who have no interest in environmental management unhappy.
- ✓ Initially, a significant expenditure is needed to develop green HR practices. It took a lot of time for staff behaviors to change.
- ✓ Measuring the effectiveness of employees' green HR initiatives presents challenges.

Suggestions

The organization's vision and goal can incorporate green HR practices. The organization bears the obligation of ensuring that employees are satisfied with their jobs and resolving environmental issues. An organization seeks to get a competitive edge. Engaging employees in green human resource management practices is a prerequisite for the organization. Organizations can effectively engage employees in their work by using Green HR practices.

SUMMARY

The corporate sector has primary responsibility for implementing green practices and proposals within their organizations. Corporate sector entities are primarily responsible for most environmental challenges. Therefore, this is the ideal moment for the organization to integrate human resource activities into the environment management system in order to improve environmental sustainability and make efficient use of natural resources. In addition, this organization prioritizes the application of green HR techniques to lower environmental pollutants, lower carbon footprints, lower costs, and improve employee involvement in green HR practices.

References

1. Bebbington, J. (2001, June). Sustainable development: a review of the international development, business and accounting literature. In *Accounting forum* (Vol. 25, No. 2, pp. 128-157). Taylor & Francis.
2. Shukla, S. S., PRIYA, U., & Joy, V. (2023, November). Green Marketing: A Social Response of Brand Communication with Customer. In 2023 3rd International Conference on Advancement in Electronics & Communication Engineering (AECE) (pp. 531-535). IEEE.
3. Berrone, P., & Gomez-Mejia, L. R. (2009). Environmental performance and executive compensation: An integrated agency-institutional perspective. *Academy of Management Journal*, 52(1), 103-126.
4. Priya, U., & Christy, A. N. A STUDY ON ROLE OF INSPECTION IN PRODUCT QUALITY AT AST INDUSTRIES, TRICHY.
5. Boiral, O. (2002). Tacit knowledge and environmental management. *Long range planning*, 35(3), 291-317.
6. Malhotra, L., Goswami, I., Kumari, P. A., & Priya, U. (2023). A study on effect of employee diversity on organizational performance. *International Journal of Professional Business Review*, 8(4), e01239-e01239.
7. Priya, U., & Mohideen, D. A. P. (2016). A Study on Attitude of Worker's towards Performance Management System at Robinsons Cargo and Logistics Pvt. Ltd., Chennai. *International Journal of Management*, 7(2), 629-635.
8. Yadav, R., Parwez, Z., Parimala, R. S., Priya, U., Rathore, S. K., & Deepak, S. S. K. (2023). Analysis and prediction of future research trends in the state of industry 5.0. *RES MILITARIS*, 13(3), 2330-2339.
9. PRIYA, U., VANITHAMANI, M., ARUN, R., VAISSHNAVE, S., THYAGARAJAN, M., & PRAKASH, K. (2023). Profitability Influencers of Indian Steel Companies: An Analytical Study. *Journal of Namibian Studies: History Politics Culture*, 35, 38-48.
10. Sivaperumal, K., Veeramani, G., Lenin, S., Deepan, A., Mishra, B. R., & Priya, U. (2024). IMPACT OF TOURISTS IN ECOTOURISM TOWARDS ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT SELECTED DESTINATIONS AT TAMIL NADU. *Journal of Digital Economy*, 3(1), 138-147.
11. KANCHANA, K., ARUN, R., DALAL, A., PRIYA, U., & UMAMAHESWARI, M. (2023). Factors Determining the Social Media Usage Among College Students in Chennai. *Journal of Harbin Engineering University*, 44(7).
12. Sivaperumal, K. (2023). A Study Focuses on the Satisfaction of Policyholders Towards the Economic Growth of Life Insurance Corporation. *European Economic Letters (EEL)*, 13(5), 755-767.

13. Sivaperumal, K., Arun, R., Natarajan, S., Raju, P., Rajeyyagari, S., & Lenin, S. (2024). Natural Language Processing in Public Communication for Migration Policies: An Ai-Driven Approach. *Migration Letters*, 21(S4), 1565-1571.
14. Arun, R., Umamaheswari, M., Monica, A., Sivaperumal, K., Natarajan, S., & Mythily, R. (2023). Effectiveness Performance of Bank Credit on the Event Management Firms in Tamilnadu State. *Data Science and Intelligent Computing Techniques*, SCRS, India, 463-470.
15. Sivaperumal, K., & Jeyachandran, T. (2019). Perception of Tourists towards Ecotourism Management Practices (With Reference to Selected Destination in TamilNadu). *Think India Journal*, 22(10), 1525-1535.
16. Prakash, K. C., Arun, R., Mayi, K., Kavitha, K., Sivaperumal, K., & Shivaratri, C. (2023). Clothing Products Purchases through Social Media Advertisements and the Problems Involved. *Remittances Review*, 8(4).
17. Umadevi, M. M., Sivaperumal, K., & Rosithabanu, M. (2019). Factors Influencing The Behavioural Intention Of Consumers Towards Online Banking Services. *Think India Journal*, 22(21), 289-296.
18. Arun, R., Bharathi, S. S., Kumar, K. A., Mishra, B. R., & Sivaperumal, K. COMMUNITY RESILIENCE IN THE FACE OF NATURAL DISASTERS: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF PREPAREDNESS AND RECOVERY STRATEGIES.
19. Shanthi, P., Prakash, K. C., Arun, R., Nirmala, C., Kousalya, M., & Sivaperumal, K. (2023). Green HRM Practices and the Factors Forcing it: A Study on Health Care Entities in Chennai. *International Journal of Professional Business Review: Int. J. Prof. Bus. Rev.*, 8(9), 25.
20. Madhumithaa, N., Mishra, A., Sruthi, S., Sivaperumal, K., & Adhav, S. (2023). Implications of Social Media and Socio-Economic Activities on Micro and Small Enterprises in India. *International Journal of Professional Business Review: Int. J. Prof. Bus. Rev.*, 8(4), 5.
21. Sivaperumal, K. (2019). A Study on The Functioning of Co-Operative Bank and Job Satisfaction of Bharat Heavy Electricals Employees' Cooperative Bank Limited, Trichy. *Think India Journal*, 22(21), 796-809.
22. Sivaperumal, K., Arun, R., Natarajan, S., Raju, P., Rajeyyagari, S., & Lenin, S. (2024). Natural Language Processing in Public Communication for Migration Policies: An Ai-Driven Approach. *Migration Letters*, 21(S4), 1565-1571.
23. Sivaperumal, K. (2023). A Study Focuses on the Satisfaction of Policyholders Towards the Economic Growth of Life Insurance Corporation. *European Economic Letters (EEL)*, 13(5), 755-767.

24. Vemuri, V. P., Sivaperumal, K., Prakash, K. C., Vimala, K., & Sudha, R. (2023). The Role of Informatics in Smart Cities: Improving Urban Sustainability and Quality of Life. *Journal of Informatics Education and Research*, 3(2).
25. CHANDRAMOULI, S., ARUN, R., MANOJKUMAR, M. A., GOPIKA, P., & SIVAPERUMAL, K. (2023). Millenials Prefernce In Fmcg Products: An Emperical Study In Chennai. *Journal of Namibian Studies: History Politics Culture*, 35, 23-37.
26. Vijayalakshmi, P., Janani, M., & Sivaperumal, K. (2019). A Study on Online Food Delivery Employees' Emotional Strength and Its Impact on Their Performance. *Think India Journal*, 22(21), 502-516.
27. Suresh, G., Sangeetha, S., & Sivaperumal, K. (2019). Emerging Trends of Human Resource Management in The Context of Global Business. *Think India Journal*, 22(21), 415-420.
28. Chittal, M. R., Umadevi, M. M., & Sivaperumal, K. (2019). Stress Management And Stress Reliving Techniques A–Review. *Think India Journal*, 22(21), 245-255.
29. Madhavi, N. B., Singh, R., Sivaperumal, K., & Rao, M. M. S. (2023, October). Sentimental Analysis Used to Find Local Events by Analysing social media. In *2023 International Conference on New Frontiers in Communication, Automation, Management and Security (ICCAMS)* (Vol. 1, pp. 1-4). IEEE.
30. Sivaperumal, D. K., Arun, D. R., & Natarajan, D. S. (2024). DR. P, S.. Rajeyyagari, and DL. S. "Natural Language Processing in Public Communication for Migration Policies: An Ai-Driven Approach". *Migration Letters*, 21(S4), 1565-71.